

**Structural and microwave absorption properties of chemical vapor deposited
MWCNTs in the 8-12 GHz region**

*Thick and Thin Film Device laboratory, Department of Physics, Shivaji University, Kolhapur -
416004, India*

Gopal Kulkarni, Ninad Velhal, Priyanka Kandesar, Vijaya Puri*

Email: vrp_phy@unishivaji.ac.in

Abstract:

In this Era, effort has been made to develop different forms of carbon using natural carbon source camphor and study their microwave absorption properties in the 8-12 GHz region. Peaks observed at $2\theta = 25.6^\circ$ and 43.5° are assigned to the graphitic phase of carbon with (002) and (100) diffraction planes. The SEM study shows the formation of MWCNTs at an optimum temperature of 900°C . After 900°C temperature, there is sudden increase in the diameter distribution of MWCNTs. TEM study depicts that at 900°C , the diameter of MWCNTs is minimum and they are contaminated with very few metal catalyst particles. In the Raman spectrum G-band centered at 1594 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of a hexagonal graphitic structure of MWCNTs. The microwave properties have been carried out in the 8-12 GHz frequency region. MWCNTs grown at 900°C shows the high reflection loss (RL) value of -33.56 dB (>99.9% power absorption) at 11.8 GHz however, they exhibit maximum SE value of -65.22 dB at 8 GHz and -46.27 dB at 10.19 GHz. Also, MWCNTs shows maximum microwave attenuation up to 65.84 dB in the 8-12 GHz frequency range.

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Vijaya Puri

Email: vrp_phy@unishivaji.ac.in